

ASSESSMENT OF THE FUTSAL INSTITUTE ACCOMPLISHMENT COACHING PROGRAM ON FEMALE FUTSAL PLAYERS: CIPPO-BASED INVESTIGATE

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Abstract

According to the results of observations and interviews with futsal coaches at Padang Futsal Academy, it was concluded that the progress of women's futsal at PFA was considered unsatisfactory when compared to other teams because there were no achievements that could be recorded. This study is intended to assess the effectiveness of the PFA futsal player talent development program by applying the CIPPO (Context, Input, Process, Product, and Outcome) method. Information was collected through observation, interview, documentation, and questionnaire methods to evaluate developments in the world of futsal sports. Data analysis was carried out using validity and CIPPO tests. This report concludes that only the standard score component in context relates positively, with inputs, processes, and products. Thus, the PFA player achievement coaching program is sufficient in its implementation because from the aspect of all components, namely context, input, process, and product, it is classified as effective. This finding has great significance and needs to be considered, because it provides valuable information regarding the achievement coaching of PFA female players or clubs that support the sport. Therefore, an in-depth analysis of existing programs is needed.

Keywords: Program Evaluation, Achievement Coaching, Futsal, Female Players, CIPPO.

INTRODUCTION

Sports coaching achievements are aimed at the progress of all sports in Indonesia, each sport has its own achievement coaching program both from the regional and national levels (Herman et al., 2024; Putra & Sepriadi, 2022; Sarikaya et al., 2024). Coaching is an effort or action taken to change a situation well to get the maximum goal to be achieved.

To achieve increased sporting achievements in various sports requires a well-structured coaching (Damrah et al., 2023; Lee et al., 2023; Sparagana et al., 2023). Optimal sports achievements can be achieved with good and correct coaching accompanied by physical, technical and mental training.

With the existence of a coaching, of course, an evaluation must also be carried out to find out the answers to the increase or decrease of an achievement in the coaching (Lavorgna et al., 2023; Miralles-Muñoz et al., 2024).

Sports achievements have a huge influence in strengthening the existence of a country so that it can help national development, as stated in a sports development journal which is an integral part of the national development process, especially in efforts to improve the quality of human resources that lead to: (1) improving the physical health of the community, (2) the mental and spiritual quality of the community,

(3) forming the character and personality of the nation, (4) discipline and sportsmanship, and (5) increasing achievements that can arouse a sense of national pride (Ilham et al., 2024; Owen et al., 2024; Sari, Kurniawan, Vicente, et al., 2023).

One of the sports that needs to be fostered and improved is the sport of Futsal. Futsal is one of the most popular sports in Indonesia and in the world. For now futsal is no longer played by male players, because now the women's team has developed a lot in Indonesia, especially in West Sumatra.

Futsal is played by 5 members from each team and is allowed to have a reserve player. Futsal uses a smaller and heavier ball compared to the ball used in soccer games (Nast et al., 2024). The futsal goal is smaller, due to the smaller size of the field, and the number of players is less than soccer (Spyrou et al., 2020).

Futsal is one type of sport that is favored by most people in West Sumatra whose development is very rapid, especially in women's futsal. Futsal games are not just done for recreational purposes and free time fillers, but have been done for optimal achievement (Alvarez et al., 2020; Wiranata et al., 2023).

This can be seen from the many futsal competitions held both at the regional and national levels. To achieve peak performance, there are many supporting factors that determine such as good physical, technical, tactical and mental conditions.

Judging from the potential, futsal games actually have the opportunity to be developed in Indonesia, because in Indonesia itself there are many potential players who are good and have skills (di Fronso et al., 2024; Ilham et al., 2024; Selviani et al., 2024; Yi et al., 2024). But of course it must also be accompanied by intensive and tiered coaching as the forerunner of the national team in the future.

Because it is impossible if a country can excel in the field of sports without intensive coaching. Intensive coaching referred to here is a coaching achievement in the field of sports that is carried out seriously and continuously to obtain optimal results (Indika et al., 2023; Qi et al., 2024; Ramanayaka et al., 2024; Sari, Bafirman, et al., 2023).

Padang Futsal Academy (PFA) is one of the schools that has many achievements, one of which is in women's futsal sports in Padang City. The Padang Futsal Academy (PFA) women's futsal team has won several events in West Sumatra and outside West Sumatra.

However, in mid-2022 until now the achievements of the Padang Futsal Academy (PFA) women's futsal team have decreased significantly. The PFA futsal team failed several times to win several tournaments held in Padang City and outside Padang City and even this team played without a single winning result.

As for some of the matches that have been followed, among others: 1. The PFA match faced BBQqueen in 2021 with a score of 1-4 so that with this score the PFA team suffered a defeat. 2. The PFA match faced IBF in 2021 with a score of 2-5 so that with this score the PFA team suffered a defeat. 3.

The PFA match faced Accasia in 2021 with a score of 2-4 so that with that score the PFA team lost. 4. The PFA match faced BBQ FC in 2022 with a score of 0-3 so that with that score the PFA team suffered a defeat. 5. The PFA match faced WKB FC in 2022 with a score of 2-3 so that with that score the PFA team suffered a defeat. 6.

The PFA match against OST Official in 2022 with a score of 1-3 so that with that score the PFA team suffered a defeat. The PFA match faced OST Sibak FC in 2022 with a score of 3-4 so that with that score the PFA team lost. The PFA match faced COD United in 2022 with a score of 5-2 so that with that score the PFA team brought victory. The PFA match faced TOXIC BBK in 2022 with a score of 4-1 so that with that score the PFA team brought victory.

In an effort to improve achievement in the sport of Futsal Padang Futsal Academy (PFA) players need regular and programmed evaluation. Evaluation is carried out to determine the achievement of the program and provide recommendations for the next training program.

The evaluation was also carried out to determine the effectiveness of the coaching program for Padang City PFA futsal players in terms of Context, Input, Process, Product and Outcome (CIPPO) variables. Researchers chose the CIPPO program evaluation because the CIPPO program evaluation model is a modification made by Gilber Sax from the CIPP model program evaluation developed by Stufflebeam (Gough et al., 2021; Novianto et al., 2022; Peinado et al., 2024; Sari, Kurniawan, Indika, et al., 2023).

Evaluation of achievement coaching using the CIPPO model is considered capable of evaluating thoroughly starting from the basis and objectives of the program, program strategy and program design, program implementation, program achievement and program impact or benefits, so that the results of the coaching program can be continued, stopped or revised.

In addition, the CIPPO model was chosen because it includes summative evaluation or carried out after the program is completed and this evaluation model is very comprehensive, when compared to other evaluation models. Thus, the evaluation of the achievement coaching program is very important so that it encourages researchers to conduct research entitled "Evaluation of the Achievement Coaching Program for Female Futsal Players of Padang Futsal Academy.

METHODS

In this study using a phenomenological qualitative approach method. The phenomenological qualitative approach has characteristics including having an actual setting, the researcher is the key instrument, the data in this study are usually descriptive, determining the process, data analysis is inductive, and the meaning of each event is an essential meaning in qualitative research. The aim is to evaluate the sports coaching of Futsal sports achievements carried out at the PFA field with an evaluation using the CIPPO model (Context, Input, Process, Product, and Outcome).

Context evaluation is used to identify and assess the needs, problems, assets that underlie the preparation of a program and try to get answers to what needs to be done. The data used in this research are qualitative and quantitative data with data collection techniques of observation, interviews, questionnaires and documentation. In this study the data used were primary and secondary data. The research informants consisted of 1 coach who doubles as a PFA coach, 1 assistant, and 6 PFA female futsal players as described in figure 1.

Figure 1: CIPPO Evaluation Model

The research instrument is described in order to explain the data that has been described through documentation guidelines, interview guidelines, and observation. Research instruments are tools used in a research activity specifically as measurement and data collection. Based on the instrument grids for components and sub-components using the CIPPO model. Where primary data is data that researchers obtain through telephone interviews and questionnaires using google forms from administrators, trainers, and coaches as research objects. While secondary data or supporting data is obtained from documentation data collection techniques.

RESULT

The Women's Futsal Performance Coaching Evaluation Program is a systematic effort that aims to measure, assess and improve the performance of a women's futsal team. The program involves various aspects, ranging from technical analysis, physical, mental, to team management. The Women's Futsal Performance Coaching Evaluation Program is a key element in the development of a competitive women's futsal team. With a comprehensive and systematic approach, the program seeks to not only improve players' technical and physical skills, but also strengthen the mental and managerial aspects of the team. Continuous evaluation and proper follow-up ensure that this coaching program can run effectively and efficiently in achieving the desired goals.

1. Context

The absence of government support points to the need for diversified funding strategies and innovative partnerships. For long-term success, consistency in training programs and adequate funding are essential, as both support the development of players' skills and optimal physical condition.

2. Input

Training programs at PFA are designed to cover physical condition, technique, tactics, and match strategy, with a fun and training approach to keep players motivated. PFA needs to conduct a comprehensive coach development program, including intensive training, workshops, and collaboration with futsal associations or football federations. By increasing the number and quality of licensed coaches, PFA can ensure optimal training, develop players' skills holistically, and enhance its reputation as a professional and competent futsal organization.

3. Process

The coaches' innovative approach and open mindset towards new training methods ensure that the training program is always relevant and effective. In addition, the good relationship between coaches and players, which creates a positive and conducive training environment, also supports player development. The achievements made by PFA's female futsal players, both at national and international levels, attest to the quality of the training programs and guidance provided. Overall, the dedication and competence of PFA's coaches play a crucial role in the development and improvement of players' achievements, making PFA the ideal place to develop a career in futsal.

4. Product

One of the key aspects of mental toughness is emotional maturity, which is the ability to manage emotions in winning or losing situations. Emotionally mature players are able to maintain emotional balance, not be easily affected by pressure, and keep thinking clearly when facing difficult situations. Experience playing in various situations also contributes to emotional maturity, helping players control fear, anxiety, and euphoria. This emotional maturity provides a strong foundation for mental toughness, which ultimately supports peak performance in a player's career.

5. Outcome

The game of futsal, especially women's futsal, has become a very popular and desirable team sport. The formation of teams in various regions with regular training schedules and good coaching shows serious efforts in improving the quality and cohesiveness of the team. The increase in the number of trained and competent female futsal players does not happen instantly, but rather through structured and sustainable coaching efforts. Coaching involves developing technical skills, physical fitness, mentality, and teamwork, with support from experienced coaches and adequate training facilities. Regular competitions are also important to measure progress and improve the quality of play. With the support of various parties such as the government, sponsors, and the community, a sustainable women's futsal ecosystem can be formed, so as to produce players who excel at the national and international levels, bringing good name to the community and country.

DISCUSSION

The CIPPO method (Context, Input, Process, Product, Outcomes) is an approach that is often used in program evaluation to understand and assess the success and effectiveness of a particular program. The following is a description of the evaluation of the women's futsal coaching program based on the CIPPO method: The discussion of the research results is an explanation of the evaluation of the coaching of the achievements of female futsal players at PFA. In this discussion section, researchers

will describe the research results in the form of interview results and relate them to existing theories. The results of the discussion regarding the evaluation of the coaching achievements of female futsal players at PFA using the CIPPO method include the following:

1. Context

The program at PFA aims to increase participation and channel hobbies in futsal sports and support the development of West Sumatra's female futsal players. It is also hoped that through a special academy for women's futsal, it can help identify and develop the talents of futsal players from a young age. Increase participation and channel hobbies in futsal sports and support the development of West Sumatra women's futsal players. In addition, it is also hoped that through a special women's futsal academy it can help identify and develop the talents of futsal players from a young age. Sport is a form of life skill that can provide good opportunities for youth life in the future. One of them is channeling hobbies in futsal sports (di Fronso et al., 2024; Izadi & Moradi, 2024; Yi et al., 2024).

Government policies in advancing sports are carried out in various efforts, among others, developing sports through promotion and management in sports, making sports policy strategies that bring success, the importance of prioritizing participation over achievement, sports as a unifying nation. Sports development in addition to playing a role in improving the degree of health and quality of life of the community also has a role in improving the welfare of the community in accordance with the direction of policies and strategic plans in determining the priority scale of national sports development (Williams et al., 2024). This statement is still inversely proportional to the situation in the PFA itself.

In the funding part of the PFA coaching process, PFA still uses personal funds, although some have received assistance from sponsors, but funding from KONI and Dispora still does not exist because PFA is still private, so that the match accommodation process relies more on the rotation of funds between players and additional sponsors.

This condition reflects a major challenge in maintaining the sustainability of a quality coaching program, considering that limited financial resources can hinder the development of adequate training and competition facilities. Furthermore, the absence of support from government agencies highlights the need for more innovative funding diversification strategies and partnerships to ensure the long-term stability and growth of the organization (Fengyingna et al., 2024; Owen et al., 2024).

This statement proves that a consistent training program and adequate funding are important factors in the sustainability of a sports club's achievements. This is in accordance with the opinion that consistent training programs ensure players can develop skills and maintain optimal physical condition, while sufficient funding allows clubs to provide facilities, equipment, and quality coaches, without these two elements, clubs will have difficulty competing at a high level. As such, the long-term success of a sports club relies heavily on investment in structured training and ongoing financial support (Fogaça et al., 2024; Krumm et al., 2023; Tinoco et al., 2023).

2. Input

The role of the coach in guiding achievement is a crucial part that must always be remembered in an achievement sports coaching program. The coach becomes the main facilitator who should always be there in an effort to improve the achievements of his players, so it is not uncommon for coach competence to be an important thing needed by an academy to advance its achievements in the future. PFA already has a coach who has a National level 1 license, but the assistant coach still does not have a license. The results of the interview show that PFA still lacks coach resources who have a license in futsal sports. The lack of coaches at PFA shows that there is still a need to increase resources again, especially in the case of coaches. The training program provided by the PFA coach is a form of physical condition training, techniques, tactics and arrangements in futsal matches. The training is more fun so that the players are not easily bored in the training process (Sepriadi et al., 2018; Xiao et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2024).

The lack of licensed coaches at PFA is not just a statistic, but a real challenge that has a direct impact on the quality of training and the development of the players. This is in accordance with the opinion of (Rohman, 2018), Without trained and licensed coaches, players may not get optimal training, which can affect their technical, tactical abilities and physical condition in the long run. Therefore, improving human resources, especially in terms of licensed coaches, should be a top priority for the PFA.

The results of the interviews conducted show that the PFA still faces a significant shortage of licensed coaches in the futsal field. This shortage reflects that the PFA still needs to make more intensive efforts to increase the number and quality of competent coaches. The need for licensed coaches is very important, considering that futsal is a sport that requires in-depth techniques, strategies, and special knowledge to be able to train players effectively (Martinen et al., 2022)

To address this issue, the PFA needs to design and implement comprehensive coach development programs. These programs could include intensive training, workshops, and courses specifically designed to meet the standards of nationally and internationally recognized futsal coach licenses. In addition, collaboration with other futsal associations or larger football federations can be a strategic step to accelerate the process of improving the quality of coaches in PFA.

The training program at PFA is fun and training, which in this case is fun so that female futsal players do not feel bored with futsal games. In addition, the training periodization at PFA is more daily, because the academy is seasonal so it cannot use monthly or annual methods. The results of the interview with the assistant coach stated that the training program for goalkeepers is different from training for futsal players, so the assistant coach here is tasked only as a coach who specifically trains goalkeepers (Brooke et al., 2020).

The training program currently provided by the coach at PFA covers various important aspects of the futsal game. The training provided includes physical condition training, basic and advanced techniques, tactics, as well as setting strategies in matches. Each of these aspects is designed to ensure that players can develop their skills holistically. Physical condition training for example, aims to improve players' endurance, strength, and agility, all of which are crucial in the fast and dynamic game of futsal (Biçer, 2021; Kuchar et al., 2023; Wooten et al., 2021).

Technical drills focus on ball control, dribbling, passing, and shooting. These techniques must be well mastered by every player so that they can play effectively and efficiently. Tactical training focuses more on understanding formations, movement without the ball, and how to deal with different game situations. In-match strategizing is also taught so that players can make the right and quick decisions during the game (Miralles-Muñoz et al., 2024)

In addition, to maintain the spirit and motivation of the players, the training program is designed to be fun. This approach aims to prevent players from getting bored during the training process. Fun training methods can include small games, challenges, and competitions between players that make the training atmosphere more lively and interesting. This approach also aims to build a good relationship between the coach and players, as well as between the players themselves. Motivation can encourage individuals to think outside the box and look for new ways to solve problems. When someone is motivated, they tend to be more persistent and do not give up easily.

3. Process

The training program provided by the PFA coach has proven to contribute positively to improving the performance and skills of the female futsal players at PFA. The players also stated that the coach at PFA has good competence in training, for example, such as having the willingness to upgrade knowledge and knowledge about futsal sports, both technically and tactically. This certainly proves that the competence of coaches at PFA has an open mind set for new things regarding the latest futsal training programs (Coleman & Eys, 2024; Fogaça et al., 2024; Zhao et al., 2024).

The training program provided by the coaches at PFA has proven to have a significant positive contribution to improving the performance and skills of female futsal players. This improvement is seen not only in the physical aspect, but also in the mastery of techniques and understanding of futsal game tactics. The players recognize that the coaches at PFA have excellent competence in training. This competence is reflected in various aspects, including in-depth knowledge of the sport of futsal, the ability to deliver training materials clearly, and the willingness to continue learning and developing themselves (Kurniawan et al., 2024). The coaches at PFA not only rely on the knowledge they already have, but also always strive to upgrade their knowledge of futsal. This includes learning the latest techniques, effective game strategies, and the latest developments in the ever-evolving world of futsal. According to the opinion (Afrizal et al., 2024), coach competition plays a role in improving a sporting achievement as well as being the main foundation for the club to be successful in the future.

One of the keys to the success of the training program at PFA is the approach taken by the coaches. They have a mindset that is open to new and innovative things in futsal training programs. This mindset is very important in the dynamic world of sports such as futsal, where changes and innovations continue to occur. According to (Ridhowi & Syafii, 2016), Coaches who are always ready to try new methods, evaluate their effectiveness, and implement them in training programs, show that the coach is not only focused on short-term achievements, but also on the long-term development of the players (Murofushi et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2024).

The female futsal players at PFA feel the positive impact of this approach. They get exercises that not only improve their physical abilities, but also enrich their understanding of the game of futsal as a whole. These exercises cover various

aspects, such as basic technique training, game strategy, physical training, as well as mental training which are all integrated in one comprehensive program. Thus, the players can develop as a whole and become better prepared for competition (Bang et al., 2024; di Fronso et al., 2024).

In addition, the relationship between coaches and players at PFA also plays an important role in the success of the training program. Coaches at PFA are known to have a good relationship with their players, providing the necessary guidance and motivation to reach their full potential. They not only act as coaches, but also as mentors and guides who are always ready to provide moral and psychological support. This creates a positive and conducive training environment, where players feel valued and motivated to keep improving.

The success of the training program at PFA can also be seen from the achievements made by the female futsal players. Many of them have managed to reach higher levels of competition, both at national and international levels. This cannot be separated from the quality of training and guidance they receive at PFA. The coaches at PFA always strive to provide the best for their players, ensuring that each player gets the attention and guidance that suits their individual needs (Blazo et al., 2024).

Overall, the training program at PFA has shown that the competence and dedication of coaches play a very crucial role in the development of female futsal players. The coaches' ability to continuously learn and adapt to change, as well as their approach to coaching, has resulted in significant improvements in the players' performance and skills. This proves that PFA is the right place for those who want to develop a career in futsal, with the support of competent coaches and innovative and effective training programs (Chen et al., 2024; McLean et al., 2021).

Coaches play a very important role in the development and improvement of player performance. Through technical guidance, motivation, emotional management, and strategic planning, coaches can help players reach their maximum potential and achieve high performance in competition. Coaches design systematic and structured training programs, which include improving physical conditions, techniques, and tactics. Training programs are usually tailored to the needs of individual players or teams, including periodization of training aimed at achieving peak performance at the right time, such as during important competitions (Lau & Mukherjee, 2023).

4. Product

Mental support for players is needed in building the performance of PFA women's futsal players. Coaches and assistant coaches at PFA always provide direction and motivational support in an effort to increase player confidence. Mental support is an essential component of modern training, it not only contributes to improved performance but also to the mental, confidence and emotional well-being of players (di Fronso et al., 2024; English et al., 2022; O'Connor et al., 2023).

Many sports experts argue that the level of successful performance is determined by the player's mental maturity and resilience in overcoming various difficulties during competition. One aspect of mental experience is determined by the level of emotional maturity. Many players are not successful in realizing their optimal abilities simply because of excessive anxiety and fear of failure. Therefore, it is important for coaches, managers and sports organizations to provide access to adequate mental support for all players (Wynters et al., 2021). A player's level of performance is often attributed to

their mental maturity and resilience in the face of challenges during a game. Many sports experts argue that the ability to stay focused, maintain concentration and cope with pressure are key factors in achieving success. This mental toughness does not come out of nowhere; it develops through experience and consistent practice (Liddelow et al., 2024; Waters et al., 2022).

One important aspect of mental toughness is emotional maturity. Emotional maturity refers to a player's ability to manage their emotions effectively, both in winning and losing situations. Players who have high emotional maturity tend to be better able to maintain emotional balance, so they are not easily affected by external or internal pressures. They are able to remain calm and think clearly when facing difficult situations, so they can make the right and quick decisions. Experience playing in a variety of situations and facing a variety of opponents also contributes to emotional maturity. Players who frequently compete at a high level learn from every experience, both positive and negative. They understand how to control fear, anxiety and euphoria. Thus, emotional maturity becomes a strong foundation for mental toughness, which ultimately helps players reach peak performance in their careers (Brooke et al., 2020; O'Connor et al., 2024; Wilcock et al., 2021).

5. Outcome

The game of futsal is a team or team sport, this futsal game is popular among the community so that many regions form a team so that they have an organized and regular training schedule and good coaching so that they can become a strong team that is compact and can get achievements. Especially in the women's futsal team, the increase in the number of trained and competent female futsal players is realized due to structured coaching efforts. Coaching can be interpreted as an effort to maintain and provoke a situation that should arise, or to maintain a situation as it should be increasing women's participation in futsal will form a sustainable women's futsal ecosystem with support from various parties (government, sponsors, community). The emergence of female futsal players who are able to compete at the national and international levels, bringing a good name to the community and country (Brooke et al., 2020; English et al., 2022; Marttinen et al., 2022; Pasqualini et al., 2024).

The game of futsal is a team sport that is very popular among the public. This popularity encourages many regions to form futsal teams, which then undergo an organized and regular training schedule and good coaching. Through this process, they strive to become a strong, cohesive and accomplished team. Special attention needs to be given to women's futsal teams, which are also showing an increase in the number of trained and competent players. This increase does not happen instantly, but through structured coaching efforts (Sari et al., 2024). Good coaching involves various aspects, ranging from technical skill development, physical fitness improvement, to mental development and teamwork. A consistent and targeted training program is essential to ensure the players get optimal training. In addition, support from experienced coaches and adequate training facilities also play a key role in the development of a women's futsal team. Regularly held competitions are also a means to measure progress and improve the quality of play. Thus, structured and sustainable coaching is essential to create a women's futsal team that is not only competitive, but also able to achieve achievements at various levels (Date et al., 2024; Miralles-Muñoz et al., 2024).

CONCLUSION

Padang Futsal Academy team shows that success in the coaching process is an important part that needs to be continuously improved. The results showed that futsal players at PFA have sufficient abilities that can be developed to become potential futsal players. The increase in the number of trained and competent female futsal players occurred thanks to well-organized coaching. The increasing participation of women in futsal will create a sustainable women's futsal ecosystem, with support from various parties such as the government, sponsors, and the community. The emergence of female futsal players who are able to compete at the national and international levels will bring good name to the community and the country. Through the use of the CIPPO method, a women's futsal coaching program can be thoroughly evaluated, ensuring that all aspects of the program from context to final outcomes are considered and assessed to achieve the expected success. Further exploration of mental support for female futsal players can help in identifying the best methods to improve players' mental toughness and emotional well-being. Future research is expected to include psychological interventions, mental training programs, and analysis of the relationship between mental toughness and player performance at various levels of competition.

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